

Co-Assessment of Community Psychology and Mental Health in the Study of Individuals

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Abstract

Outside the study of individuals, community psychology looks at problems with mental health and interpersonal relationships in communities. Community psychologists assist people in achieving their objectives by working in contexts like community projects and health and well-being programs. The following are some instances in which a health care psychologist's skills may be needed. It is conducted in order to provide crucial diagnostic therapies and preventative interventions for psychological issues in primary health care, illness prevention, and behavioral health promotion. This comprises psychological evaluations and diagnoses, psychological therapy, and improvement-focused aftercare services. These services are available to persons of all ages as

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well as to those who fit into certain categories. This group includes people with exceptional needs, such as those who struggle with learning, have brain injury, or are mentally retarded. Children, teenagers, adults, elderly, and all other age groups will be covered by this. healthcare in the tertiary A psychologist might be an important member of a patient's treatment team if they are dealing with the psychological effects of an acute or long-term life-threatening illness like cancer, respiratory or renal problems. Clinical neuropsychologists are also becoming increasingly important in the identification, evaluation, patient care, and cognitive rehabilitation of those who have brain injury. For psychologists working in healthcare settings like hospitals and other medical institutes, independent or collaborative work is a possibility. They start off as clinical psychologists before transitioning into positions as mental health specialists. They often work in mental health centers and psychiatric hospitals. Second, they are behavioral health practitioners who deal with both physical sickness and psychological elements of health because they are health or medical psychologists. This feature of their work distinguishes them from others. They provide clinical and healthcare services to patients who can function independently as well as to new patients who need to be checked via inpatient and outpatient treatment programs. They also assist patients who are already able to care for themselves.

Keywords: *Community Psychology, Mental Health, Personal Habits, Personality Psychology, Psychological Examination of the Individual*

Introduction

1. *Services that psychologists provide typically include:*
2. *diagnosis and evaluation,*
3. *Intervention and treatment,*
4. *Consultation with other professionals and others*
5. *program development,*
6. *supervision,*
7. *Management,*
8. *Psychological services and the evaluation and planning of these services,*
9. *In addition, teaching and researching all these areas and contributing to knowledge.*

Evaluation

In healthcare settings like hospitals and primary care offices, clinical assessment is a crucial component of a psychologist's profession. For several reasons, they employ assessment tools including psychological testing. Assessing current functioning, for instance, can be used to diagnose relationship conflicts, adjustment, learning differences, educational potential, career interest, etc., as well as to diagnose abnormal behaviors and non-psychiatric problems such as depression, psychosis, personality disorders, dementia, etc.; determine treatment needs; choose an appropriate treatment; provide a prognosis; monitor treatment; and treat depression. Psychologists use psychometric tests, which are standardized and validated tools that evaluate a wide range of functions including intelligence, personality, cognitive neuropsychology, motivations, abilities, and the severity of mental health problems, among other things, to diagnose abnormal behaviors. One of the tests utilized is behavioral evaluation and observation, which also includes rating scales.

1. *intellectual assessments such as IQ tests.*
2. *neuropsychological tests such as Halstead Reitan tests; personality scales (objective and projective tests).*
3. *Diagnostic interviews (structured and semi-structured).*
4. *psychophysiological and biobehavioral monitoring such as biofeedback.*
5. *mental status examinations.*
6. *Forensic evaluations.*
7. *psycho-educational measures and professional tests.*
8. *and mental health assessments.*

The use of psychological tests, as well as its administration and interpretation, are only permitted by certified psychologists. This is true for those who work in mental and physical health.

Treatment

One of the most crucial things psychologists perform when it comes to delivering healthcare is intervention or therapy. To help those coping with physical and mental health concerns, they provide a comprehensive variety of therapeutic therapies to individuals, groups, couples, and

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families. The primary causes of human misery and dysfunction are emotional conflicts, personality disorders, psychopathology, and skill deficiencies. These therapies attempt to prevent, cure, and overcome these issues.

Conceptual Framework

They provide a broad range of psychological therapies, such as CBT, behavior modification, family and marital therapy, biofeedback, healing, group psychotherapy, psychoanalysis, client-centered therapy, pain management, neuropsychological healing, interpersonal psychotherapy, and others. Less than 25% of patients who see their doctor with physical concerns have known or visible organic or biological symptoms, according to research. However, a sizable portion of patients' physical or medical complaints (functional symptoms) cannot be medically explained yet nonetheless respond well to psychological therapy.

Therefore, psychological treatments are helpful in terms of enhancing one's quality of life and physical as well as mental health. Also, these therapies are economical.

consultations

Many psychologists are professionals who operate in the medical field, in business, in educational institutions, in nonprofit organizations, in communities, etc. offers services for psychological treatment. For instance, a psychologist may help a doctor better handle patients who refuse to comply with uncomfortable medical treatments. This may be quite beneficial. A company owner might see a qualified psychologist for guidance when they need assistance with stress management or lowering workplace tensions. Psychologists may include assessment, teaching, research, and therapy in their consultations.

Administrative Advantages and Powers

Because of their grasp of human behavior, psychologists are regarded as exceptionally skilled and competent managers. Psychologists often work in administrative positions in hospitals and other inpatient settings because they hold the conviction that comprehending human behavior in social contexts is the foundation of management. Psychologists may take on managerial responsibilities in hospitals, preside over divisions including neuropsychology, mental health, rehabilitation, and

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occupational health. Graduate education program directors may come from the fields of mental health, student counseling and psychological services, hospital outpatient departments, or hospital directors. These roles all have something to do with mental health. Also, they participate in the committees that are allocated to them and are active members of their departments. Management psychologists oversee overseeing multidisciplinary professional and support personnel, formulating rules and procedures for planning and staffing issues, and doing other administrative tasks.

Lastly, they take part in and contribute to every aspect of quality management in hospitals and other care facilities.

Including Teaching and Training A Significant Part of Time

A sizable percentage of the time spent by psychologists working in medical settings is spent on academic pursuits (education and training). In all psychology, human behavior, and behavioral science courses included in undergraduate and graduate medical, dental, nursing, and other allied health curricula, they educate psychology students, trainees, residents, and healthcare professionals.

They educate health professionals as well. Both management and research are audited. Because of their education and credentials, clinical and health psychologists value research. These are some examples of the many kinds of research they do:

- (a) *diagnostic evaluation tests and examination of their reliability and validity.*
- (b) *adapting and testing the effectiveness of both psychological and biological interventions to promote health and overcome disorders.*
- (c) *studies to reveal the cultural and cross-cultural aspects of psychological abnormalities; And*
- (d) *detecting the impact of both positive and negative human behaviors and attitudes; Examples of research activities:*

Qualifications Obtained Through Education

A bachelor's degree in psychology is required for certification as a clinical health psychologist. Together with clinical research, courses on human growth and development, personality,

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individual differences, typical and abnormal behavior, biological, cognitive, social, and cultural factors, psychometric and psychological tests, experimental layouts, and statistics are also crucial.

It is crucial and required to complete postgraduate coursework (master's and doctorate degrees) in clinical or health psychology. It is strongly advised that you immediately pursue a postdoctoral fellowship with a focus on clinical or health psychology after completing this phase.

Concerns Regarding One's Career and Practice

Almost all facets of the healthcare delivery system have been affected by the psychology discipline. Therefore, psychologists are acknowledged as offering necessary, significant, and affordable health services in the majority of communities. Nonetheless, psychologists are regarded as a privileged member of the medical team in hospitals. Moreover, several nations now permit psychologists to write psychiatric medicine prescriptions.

These results show that the program can teach licensed psychologists to provide pharmacological therapy in a safe, effective, and reasonably priced manner. Presenting these data demonstrated the program's effectiveness in achieving its primary goal.

The National Psychological Societies are requesting that laws be passed that would let psychologists to prescribe after completing a specialized degree in psychopharmacology. Important associations have organized a task force on psychopharmacology to help this endeavor by teaching psychologists how to function as prescribers.

Notwithstanding this, a sizable portion of psychologists believe that in actual practice, their field should be maintained as distinct from psychiatry as feasible. They contend that this is so because psychologists, as medical professionals, have access to therapeutic options that are supported by research and are equally as effective as psychotropic medications. Regarding ethics Psychologists follow a set of moral principles and regulations of behavior, much as other healthcare practitioners.

This,

- a) *general principles (such as respect for human rights and dignity, the welfare of others and social responsibility) and*

- b) *It consists of specific ethical standards regarding their roles in relation to patients and their experiments.*

Method

Competence, honesty, professional and scientific accountability, respect for human rights and dignity, and consideration for others' well-being are only a few examples of general principles. Visit this page to see our suggestions. In the United States, Europe, and several emerging nations, the integration of biological and behavioral sciences in medical education and practice is now a reality. All these areas are covered by this.

This study examines the evolution of the field, important players and venues that progress research on the mental health and well-being of university students, and the field's structure using several bibliometric indicators based on publication and citation patterns. The fields that form the basis of the field's foundations and recurrent research subjects mentioned in the literature are examples of patterns of scientific partnerships. As a result, this research employs a variety of bibliometric indices to investigate the development of the area based on patterns in publishing and citation. This is crucial because, despite significant advancements, the corpus of information about studies on mental health and wellbeing is still varied and dispersed (Pellmar and Eisenberg, 2000; Bailey, 2012; Wittchen et al. 2014a).

Certainly, mental health and well-being are abstract notions with a complicated genesis and history that draw on different viewpoints and contributions from a wide range of fields and situations. For these reasons, as well as others, mapping research on the mental health and well-being of college students is essential.

“Identifying contributions and challenges to the development of the field; help guide policy, research and practice towards areas, areas, populations and contexts that need further investigation; and better care for students attending higher education institutions (Naveed et al. 2017).”

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A Statement on the Conceptualization of Mental Health, Mental Illness, and Well-Being

In today's culture, the idea of mental health is not one that is well understood or embraced. For a long time, the terms "mental disease" and "mental health" have been used interchangeably (Manwell et al., 2015). But, in today's culture, mental health and mental disease are viewed as two distinct ideas. The literature distinguishes between mental health and sickness from two major approaches. The continuum approach considers that mental health and mental disease are two extremes of a continuum that may be seen as a scale. Yet between these two extremes, there exist a wide range of degrees of health and disease, and most individuals fall somewhere in the middle. The categorical technique, on the other hand, depicts mental health and sickness as a dichotomy in the two representations. Those who exhibit symptoms of mental illness are categorized as belonging to that group and given the relevant label, while individuals who do not exhibit these symptoms are seen to be mentally sound (Scheid & Brown, 2010).

Multidisciplinary Perspectives on How to Conceptualize Mental Health and Illness

Emerging conceptualizations are significantly influenced by the theoretical and paradigmatic foundations of the disciplines that give rise to various conceptualizations of mental health and sickness. With the information generated in a broad range of sub-fields within the biological, behavioral, and social sciences, the discipline has expanded enormously in this setting. medical standards, diseases, and

(a) (a) It emphasizes normalcy, and since biological disciplines are anchored on this paradigm, they often highlight the duality of mental health and sickness (Scheid & Brown, 2010). In this field, research on mental health and wellbeing has historically been done from a psychiatric viewpoint. This field of study strives to develop a pharmaceutical remedy for neuronal dysfunctions as well as an understanding of the brain dysfunction that causes psychiatric symptoms. Because of this, psychiatrists have typically thought of mental illness as a brain disease (such as depression) caused by hereditary, biological, or neurological factors, comparable to any other physical ailment (Schwartz & Corcoran, 2010). While it is undeniable that psychiatric approaches to mental health are now more prevalent than other methods, the development of other biological disciplines has

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significantly advanced this subject in recent years. Examples include the claim made by Insel and Wang (2010) that advances in genetics and neuroscience "help reconceptualize mental diseases as brain disorders and so alter the practice of psychiatry." (1979). Also, even though there are ongoing discussions about whether behavioral medicine and mental health should be treated as two distinct areas of study, behavioral medicine has also significantly advanced the profession (Dekker et al. , 2017).

(b) (b) A branch of behavioral sciences known as the study of mental health focuses on the many psychological systems and processes that cause thoughts, emotions, and behaviors (Peterson, 2010). The oldest tradition in the psychological study of mental health belongs to clinical psychology, which focuses on diagnosing and treating mental diseases and illnesses that might lessen psychological suffering or encourage good states of being. This may be accomplished by emphasizing strategies for fostering optimistic states of being or easing psychological suffering (Haslam & Lusher, 2011).

(c) (c) Despite this, important contributions to the subject have come from other areas of psychology that don't place as much emphasis on psychopathology. Psychoanalysis, humanistic psychology, cognitive psychology, personality and social psychology are some of these subfields (Peterson, 2010). While there are many theories, philosophies, and methodological methods to understanding mental health, behavioral sciences emphasize sustained approaches to mental health because they acknowledge that mental health has a biological base and is in a social context (Scheid & Brown, 2010).

The study only included articles that appeared in publications between 1975 and 2020. (including both). There are no language-based restrictions on the search:

“ After removing duplicates, a total of 5,561 research papers were retrieved. Because of the search, the authors of each document that was found gathered data on the article's title, publication year, journal, number of citations, as well as the authors' names, organizations, and countries. ”

Data Analysis Methods

The literary corpus was then subjected to a descriptive and bibliometric analysis to provide a comprehensive picture of the history and present status of research on mental health and wellbeing in academic contexts. The number of publications and citations for each year was gathered to plot the evolution of research on university students' mental health and wellbeing. Ordinal tables were used to examine the productivity of the field as measured by the main journals and research topics, as well as the important scientists and countries that contributed to the development of the subject. To define the area, these tables were made.

Findings

Bibliometric studies were performed using the VOSViewer application to explore the social, intellectual, and conceptual structure of the area and to visually depict it. VOSViewer is open-source software that may be used to evaluate and create bibliometric maps. It can be downloaded for free. Journals, publications, citations, authors, and even countries may be used as units of analysis in VOSViewer, depending on the study's specific topic. In each map, circular nodes that stand in for units of analysis may be observed. The node's size (for instance, the number of articles published by one individual in the dataset) gives an idea of its volume, and its placement on the map shows how comparable it is to other nodes. Nodes that are more closely spaced apart from one another share more information. The application uses a distance-based methodology to create bibliometric maps in three steps (Van Eck & Waltman, 2014). The software starts by standardizing the discrepancies that occur between the nodes. The program builds a two-dimensional map in the process' second stage, where the distances between the nodes indicate how closely they are connected to one another. The following action taken by VOSViewer is to group tightly coupled nodes (Van Eck and Waltman, 2014).

Many kinds of co-authorship have been used in studies on college students' mental health and wellbeing. These analyses were conducted to look at the social organization of such research. For these research, the unit of analysis was the authors and their country or area. The "lines" connecting each "node" on the map represent the relationships that exist between the different "nodes," and each "node" on the map represents an author or a nation/regional organization.

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Clusters are visual representations of scientific cooperation networks that may be thought of as associations of authors or countries who often publish together (for example, research groups in the case of authors). A collaborative citation research of the journals was conducted to look into the intellectual landscape of the area. In this instance, the dataset's journals served as the units of analysis, and the map displays the connections that often cite different journals. A third journal is co-cited if it cites both of these periodicals. It is believed that the more often the two journals are cited in a third publication, the stronger the common citation relationship between the two journals is.

Literature review

There is a presumption that works that are often quoted by one another possess similar theoretical and semantic underpinnings. Therefore, the groups of articles that are commonly mentioned in our study may be regarded as the fields that serve as the foundation for research on university students' mental health and wellbeing. Lastly, a keyword coexistence analysis was conducted to comprehend the conceptual framework of the topic. The authors' chosen keywords served as the units of analysis in this specific case. The likelihood that both keywords will appear in the same record increases with the strength of the co-occurrence relationship between the two phrases.

The keyword clusters that appeared together in this study reflect 45 years' worth of research on university students' mental health and wellbeing.

Growth Path

Throughout the last 45 years, there has been a steady rise in academic interest in the mental health of university students, which may be divided into three periods. The first calls for attention to the rise and severity of university students' mental issues and help-seeking behaviors occurred 15 years ago, at the same time as the number of publications has steadily increased (Kadison & DiGeronimo, 2004; Evans et al., 2018).

This could indicate a rise in interest in researching the prevalence of mental illnesses and the function universities serve in fostering students' mental health and wellbeing. A model very similar to the one described above can be found both in absolute terms and as a proportion of all articles

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published in medicine and across disciplines, according to the findings of a recent bibliometric study (Larivière et al., 2013), which examined global research on mental health in both absolute terms and as a percentage of all articles published across disciplines and in medicine (Larivière et al., 2013).

Another significant area of research in this subject is psychiatry, which accounts for around 20% of papers. Another important contributor (15%) to the overall number of publications in this field is the literature on education and educational research. The fields of public environmental occupational health, drug addiction, general internal medicine, neuroscience neurology, health care science services, and nursing are other pertinent study topics in the subject of health and medicine. Health and medicine-related research fields also fall under this category. The field is also supported, although to a lesser extent, by publications from family studies, social work research, and social science magazines. This last item is very crucial.

Total enrolment is used to determine the top research fields. Most of the study on the mental health and wellbeing of college students is, according to productivity analysis for journals and research fields, "in the disciplines of psychology." journals for psychiatry and psychology (McAvoy, 2014). This conclusion is similar with that of earlier studies on general population mental health (eg, Haslam & Lusher, 2011). Yet, the findings of our investigation indicated that almost twice as much research was published in psychological journals as it was in psychiatric journals. According to Haslam and Lusher (2011), psychiatry journals have a bigger influence on mental health research than clinical psychology publications do, and they also gather more research and citations on the subject. This result runs counter to what they found. This is since our analysis included publications from all psychological subfields, unlike the research of Haslam and Lusher, which only included journals in clinical psychology. Moreover, counseling clinics run and staffed by non-medical professionals generally provide mental health services in higher education (such as psychologists, social workers, counselors, and family therapists). Instead of diagnosing and treating symptoms, these non-medical practitioners often adopt developmental practice models based on behavioral sciences that emphasize compliance concerns, vocational training, employment, and other personal requirements (LeViness et al., 2018; Mitchell et al., 2019).

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This is over ten times more publications than those published in China, which is now ranked second and contributed around 6% of the dataset's total quantity of research. The last three spots on this list, which are occupied by Canada (265 entries), Australia (254 entries), and the United Kingdom, are filled by those three countries. Among all these nations/regions, Canada has the highest enrolment (243). The remaining nations are in West Asia (Iran), Africa (South Africa), East Asia (South Korea), and Europe (Spain, Germany, and Turkey) (Japan). In several places of the globe, there is at least some worry about the percentage of college students. The productivity analysis for authors and nations revealed that studies on the wellbeing and mental health of university students were conducted all over the globe.

After analyzing the aggregate data for authors and nations, we came to this result. This should not be surprising given that these countries have better research infrastructure and resources than other countries (Wong et al., 2006), as well as a longer history of mental health studies in general (Gopalkrishnan). Despite this, Larivière et al. (2013) discovered that since 1980, the United States has seen a sharp reduction in the amount of mental health research it produces, compared to two other English-speaking nations (the United Kingdom and Canada). On the other hand, the number of publications coming from European nations has greatly expanded, and the five biggest growing national economies—Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa—now account for roughly half of all publications worldwide.

Argument

However, it's possible that a large portion of the knowledge created in the industrialized world today is based on psychological and psychiatric viewpoints. This may obscure the divergent views on mental health and wellbeing that are common in other regions of the globe and eventually hinder the creation of successful programs that are more suited to meet regional conventions, values, and needs. LMICs (Timimi, 2010; Summerfield, 2013). (Timimi, 2010; Summerfield, 2013). The social structure is made up of networks of scientific collaboration. Collaboration in research is generally recognized as a way to boost research production and academic influence, as well as a way to assess the overall quality of the work (Kim, 2006; Abramo et al., 2009). Especially, it is acknowledged that the involvement of foreign scholars in collaborative research

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projects plays a crucial role in both the social construction of science and the advancement of many scientific disciplines (Coccia and Wang, 2016). According to current data, national and international research partnerships have significantly risen recently, particularly in practical domains like health and the humanities (Gazni et al., 2012; Wagner et al., 2015). Wagner et al. (2015); Gazni et al. (2012) 2016 (Coccia and Bozeman). Co-authorship research were conducted to ascertain the patterns of scientific collaboration between academics from various nations and regions on university students' mental health and wellbeing. This shows the presence of several successful academic collaboration networks made up of five or more academics who have significantly advanced the topic. A multinational research group of 15 scholars connected to universities in the United States, Belgium, and the Netherlands makes up the biggest collaborative network. Several of the most well-known experts on the topic are represented in this cluster, including RP Auerbach, R. Brauffaerts, RC Kressler, P. Cuijpers, and others. An extensive global initiative called the WHO Global Mental Health International University Student (WMH-ICS) Initiative aims to enhance the mental health and general wellbeing of university students all over the globe.

The dissemination of evidence-based therapies, the creation of web-based interventions for mental health prevention and promotion, and the generation of epidemiological data on mental health issues among university students globally will accomplish this.

The results suggest that closeness in terms of culture, language, and geography is vital in defining how international collaboration in the area is considerably organized. Overall, our study's results indicate that local-level cooperation in research on university students' mental health and wellbeing is very unusual. At the level of the author, the social structure of the site may be likened to an archipelago of variously sized and composed islands. Yet, there aren't many bridges connecting these islands, which illustrates how dispersed the scientific community is. The analysis also demonstrated the existence of international networks for collaboration; however, it also demonstrated that these networks are built between researchers in neighboring countries or regions, across national boundaries, or between nations with comparable cultural, linguistic, and historical legacies. This could be the case because various contexts prioritize certain cultural and traditional values differently when deciding how to construct mental health and wellbeing (Eshun

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& Gurung, 2009; Vaillant, 2012; Fernando, 2019). Language disparities, various international institutional and organizational traditions, and extracurricular participation have higher expenses in addition to what has been shown to impede the growth and sustainability of research partnerships in health research (Hooper et al, 2005; Freshwater et al, 2006). However, it is debatable whether a lack of research collaboration, both within and between nations, poses obstacles to the development of a field in terms of missed opportunities to question widely held beliefs and move toward alternative viewpoints, to push the boundaries of methodologies and techniques, and to interact with diverse groups. Addressing common mental health concerns requires bringing together and integrating individuals from various cultural backgrounds, as well as exchanging information, skills, and resources (Rolfe et al., 2004; Freshwater et al., 2006). The disciplines that support the fundamental building blocks of the field make up the intellectual structure. The complex and multidimensional nature of health and well-being is often seen as an area where interdisciplinarity might be helpful (Mabry et al., 2008). The intersection of the medical, psychological, and social sciences, according to Buckton (2015), has contributed to "new views on theory, practice, and research in mental health and development."

Journal co-citation analysis was used to examine the subject areas that serve as the foundation for research on the mental health and wellbeing of university students. For this research (n = 593), only works with at least 50 citations apiece were considered. The amount of common citation relationships that a journal has with other journals determines how important that journal is. The study's overall conclusions point to the fact that research on college students' mental health and wellbeing is, at least in part, multidisciplinary and stems from the fusion of work done largely in the behavioral and biological sciences (Schumann et al., 2014; Wittchen et al., 2014b). To be more specific, the map illustrates how data from five linked disciplines are combined to examine university students' mental health and well-being.

The yellow cluster at the top of the page is where journals regarding drug and alcohol misuse, addiction, and issues related to interpersonal violence are gathered.

This discovery is not unexpected given the historical contributions of biological disciplines to the area of mental health research (Schwartz & Corcoran, 2010). The subject of behavioral sciences

seems to be heavily influenced by personality and social psychology (Sánchez Moreno and Barrón López de Roda, 2003), which investigates the ways in which social occurrences impact mental health and wellbeing. This is since social psychology and personality studies aim to comprehend how social phenomena impact mental health and wellbeing. Unexpectedly, clinical psychology journals are in the middle of the map and exhibit co-citation links with journals from every other cluster. Yet, compared to other journals in the area, clinical psychology journals have the least number of co-citation linkages and the most scattered network. This indicates, as Haslam and Lusher write, that clinical psychology papers bend more to journals in other areas in terms of citation streams and eventually play a less prominent role in studies on the mental health and wellbeing of college students (2011). It is noteworthy to note that research from the social sciences (such as sociology and anthropology) does not significantly advance the field's body of knowledge. This study suggests that there is still much to learn about how social circumstances and cultures (such as inequality, social norms, governmental policies, cultural ideas and values) affect the mental health and well-being of university students. Despite this, it is fascinating to see the density of co-citation network interactions both inside and across clusters. This is particularly true considering the disparities between the medical, psychological, and social reasons for mental suffering and the lack of a shared philosophy of practice in the field of mental health (Bailey, 2012).

Conclusion

Things that don't fit into any of the sets already in existence or have no connection to other items are taken out. The thickness of the edges corresponds to the strength of the co-occurrence link between various keyword combinations, while the size of the nodes corresponds to the frequency with which author keywords exist in the dataset. More generally, the seven overarching themes seem to be able to describe the 45-year-long thematic emphasis on the mental health and wellbeing of university students. The employment of words like "well-being," "self-esteem," "life satisfaction," "social support," and "emotional" shows that there has been an increasing emphasis on maintaining good mental health. The second subject that has received a lot of attention in published research is mental illness, with an emphasis on depressed and anxious states and, to a

lesser degree, suicidal and suicidal ideation states. Alcohol abuse was a specific focus of this study's third theme, which was drug abuse. The fourth issue covers collegiate counseling for mental health, including both protective and preventative factors like mindfulness, stress reduction, spirituality, and getting assistance when necessary.

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